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Proportional Integral For Two-Stage Battery Controller Based Smell Agent Optimization

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces Fruit fly Optimization Algorithm Proportional Integral (FOA-PI) controller, which is developed to manage battery regulation through a two-stage control method. Given the rapid growth in renewable energy adoption and the rising use of electric vehicles, effective battery management systems are essential for optimizing energy usage. The FOA-PI controller control to improve the management of battery charge and discharge cycles. Its performance is assessed through simulations and a comparative study using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) metric, revealing a 6.91% enhancement in battery current control compared to the conventional PI controller. This work advances battery management technology, offering a solution to enhance energy efficiency in response to evolving energy systems and technological progress

Keywords: Optimized Proportional Integral Controller, Two-Stage Battery System, Fruit fly Optimization Algorithm (FOA) Algorithm, Battery management, Proportional Integral (PI) Control.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of electric vehicles (EVs) and renewable energy systems (RESs) is largely driven by the global effort to reduce environmental pollution and dependence on nonrenewable energy sources (Sarsia et al., 2023). Batteries play a key role as the main energy storage units for both RESs and EVs. Among them, lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) stand out for their high performance and steadily decreasing cost. Nevertheless, LIBs often face harsh operating conditions and various forms of misuse. Factors such as overloading, external heat exposure, rapid charging, and internal or external short circuits can lead to abnormal temperature increases, gas generation, or even thermal runaway, combustion, and explosions, all of which shorten battery lifespan. Therefore, proper battery management is essential to ensure safety and prolong service life. A battery management system (BMS) is crucial for continuously monitoring

battery states and ensuring that performance remains adequate throughout the battery's operational lifetime (Costa et al., 2021)

An essential component of battery management is the regulation of charging and discharging processes to enhance efficiency and prolong battery life. Various control systems have been introduced to automate this regulation, including proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controllers, fuzzy logic controllers, sliding mode controllers, and proportional-integral (PI) controllers (Lee et al., 2021).

The Proportional-Integral (PI) controller is one of the traditional methods frequently applied in battery control because of its simplicity and reliability. However, batteries exhibit hysteresis and a nonlinear charging circuit, making precise control challenging. The conventional PI tuning process is often complex, relying on empirical formulas and multiple experiments to adjust the PID parameters. Achieving optimal parameter settings is difficult, resulting in a control system with a long response time and significant overshoot, which fails to meet the demands of current control (Zainurin et al., 2021). Accurate regulation of charging parameters—such as voltage and current—in lithium batteries can reduce charging time, enhance efficiency, extend battery lifespan, and lower costs. Consequently, optimizing PI parameter tuning in the battery charging circuit holds great importance (Liu et al., 2022)

In this study, an optimized Proportional-Integral (PI) controller is developed for a two-stage battery model to improve the regulation of charging and discharging processes. To enhance the controller's performance, the PI gain parameters are optimized using the Fruit Fly Optimization Algorithm (FOA)

2.0 Problem Statement/Justification

A Battery Management System (BMS) plays a crucial role in ensuring the safe operation of devices powered by lithium-ion batteries. Effective battery management entails controlling the charging and discharging processes to enhance efficiency and prolong battery life. Among the traditional control methods, the Proportional-Integral (PI) control technique is widely utilized for managing these processes. However, while the PI controller can stabilize the battery's state of charge to a certain extent, its performance in terms of root mean square error (RMSE) for current control remains unsatisfactory due to uncertainties that arise during charging and discharging. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the performance of the PI control method to further boost efficiency and extend battery longevity. To achieve this, the present research proposes an optimized Proportional-Integral controller for a two-stage battery system aimed at enhancing the regulation of charging and discharging processes while preventing energy overloads and deep discharges that could damage the battery. The optimization of PI gain parameters will be carried out using a metaheuristic approach—the Fruit Fly Optimization Algorithm (FOA) within a well-structured optimization framework. This approach is intended to ensure safe and efficient energy management in the face of evolving energy demands and technological developments.

3.0 Objectives Of The Study

In order to achieve the stated aim of the research, the following objectives are set.

1. To develop the Simulink model of two-stage battery model.
2. To develop an optimized FOA-PI controller for the developed the Simulink model (1).
3. To evaluate the performance of the developed system with the research of Muritala et al., (2024) using DC voltage regulation, battery voltage and battery reference control as performance metrics

4.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews and discusses several studies related to the present research. The reviewed literature covers previous work on battery management systems (BMS), various battery control methods, and optimization algorithms applied in BMS development.

Kumar and Dinesh (2020) explored the concept and implementation of a battery management system for electric vehicles, with the primary objective of preventing battery cell misuse and damage. Their study involved the design and realization of an active clamp forward converter for active cell balancing, as well as the development of a new BMS platform utilizing dedicated integrated circuits and microcontrollers optimized for fast sampling, high accuracy, low power consumption, and low cost. The BMS topology and the active forward converter were simulated using Or CAD, TINA, and MATLAB Simulink

software. Simulation results indicated that with an input voltage of 40 V, the converter produced an output voltage of 3.3 V at 90% efficiency, with voltage ripple limited to below 5%. The proposed BMS topology was further validated by printing the PCB and testing it with a connected battery stack during both charging and discharging processes for active cell balancing

Ibrahim et al. (2022) developed an artificial pancreas model based on a genetic-fuzzy proportional-integral (fuzzy-PI) control technique for two-stage battery regulation. Because the fuzzy-PI controller is suitable only for linear systems, the researchers first linearized the bidirectional converter model using a gap metric before applying the controller. The proposed approach utilized a triangular membership function with three linguistic variables Low (L), Medium (M), and High (H). Simulation results of the two-stage battery model showed that the proposed controller achieved superior performance in DC voltage regulation, battery voltage control, and battery reference tracking compared to the conventional fuzzy-PI controller. However, the study also reported that the resulting battery voltage was relatively high.

Singh et al. (2023) focused on the design and control of a two-stage on board battery charger (OBC) for low-voltage electric vehicles (LVEVs). The developed charger featured a high power factor and the ability to operate efficiently over a wide range of AC input voltages. At the input stage, a bridgeless AC–DC converter with constant input current characteristics was implemented, while an isolated Ćuk DC–DC converter was used at the output stage to regulate various battery charging modes, employing constant voltage (CV) and constant current (CC) charging profiles. The system’s performance in terms of DC voltage regulation, battery voltage, and battery current control was compared against other modern power factor correction (PFC) topologies. Both simulation and experimental results validated the effectiveness and overall operational performance of the proposed design.

Muritala et al. (2024) developed a Single Input Interval Type-2 Fuzzy Logic Proportional-Integral (SIIT2FL-PI) controller designed to regulate battery operation using a two-stage control strategy. In this approach, a lithium battery model was first created in MATLAB/Simulink before integrating the SIIT2FL-PI controller to enhance the control of charging and discharging processes. As the method is applicable primarily to linear systems, the proposed two-stage battery model was simulated and evaluated against a conventional PI controller. The simulation results demonstrated that the proposed controller outperformed the traditional PI controller, achieving a 31% improvement in root mean square error (RMSE) for battery current control, along with better DC voltage regulation, battery voltage stability, and reference tracking performance.

From the reviewed studies, it is clear that considerable research has been devoted to improving the regulation of charging and discharging control in lithium batteries. This has led to the development of various battery management system (BMS) controllers, such as PID, IBC, LQR, FLC, and SMC controllers. Most of these studies have primarily focused on addressing issues related to battery voltage or high DC voltage regulation. However, limited attention has been given to maintaining consistent reference battery control, which is essential for effectively managing charging and discharging operations. Hence, this study is built upon the objective of developing an optimized Proportional-Integral (PI) controller for a two-stage battery system, utilizing the Fruit Fly Optimization Algorithm (FOA) to enhance control performance within a BMS framework

5.0 METHODOLOGY

In this section, step-by-step procedures leading to the implementation of the stated objectives are discussed based on the following assumptions:

5.1 Designing Simulink model of Two-stage Battery Model

Figure 6: Model of a Boost Converter (Kumar et al., 2019)

The transfer capability of boost converter depends upon the inductor (L_{boost}) and capacitor (C_{boost}) as shown in Figure 1 The output voltage (V_{DC}), L_{boost} and C_{boost} value is obtained as (Kumar et al., 2019):

$$V_{DC} = \frac{1}{1-D_b} V_{pv} \tag{1}$$

$$L_{boost} = \frac{V_{DC} D_b}{\Delta I_L f} \tag{2}$$

$$C_{boost} = \frac{V_{PV} D_b}{R_o \Delta V_{PV} f} \tag{3}$$

Where V_{pv} , $\Delta I_{L,f}$, R_o and R_o are the input voltage, inductor ripple current, switching frequency, capacitor ripple voltage and output impedance of boost converter respectively. Equations (1) to (4), which describe current, SOC, voltage, and amplitude, respectively, are the mathematical model of the two-stage battery system. The model was modeled in Simulink for both the charging and discharging modes. To represent the boost converter, as shown in the Figure below, equations (1) to (2) were also utilized. Figure 2 displays the two-stage battery's Simulink model after it was developed.

Figure 7: Simulink Model of Charging and Discharging.

Table 1 shows the values of Lithium battery model parameters used in this work.

Table 1: Lithium Battery Parameters (Muritala et al., 2024)

Parameter	Value	Unit
Nominal voltage	0.072	V
Rated capacity	0.0005	Ah
Initial state of charge	0.00021	%
Battery response time	0.5	S
Battery nominal discharge current	0.002	A

5.2 Development FOA-PI controller for the Two-stage Battery system

To develop the PI based two-stage battery control system; there is the need to obtain the best possible combination of the PI gain parameters.

5.2.1 To designed PI controller in MATLAB/Simulink

The control scheme was developed in this section. It is made up of the integral and proportional parts. The PI control law function can be state as:

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int e(t)dt \quad (4)$$

The resulting Simulink model is showing below:

Figure 8: Simulink Model of PI Controller.

The Simulink diagram of the PI controller with two (2) controller parameters (k_p and k_i).is shown in Figure 3.The Fruitfly Optimization Algorithm (FOA) was created in order to determine the PI controller's ideal parameters. This algorithm's goal function is based on the controller gains (k_p and k_i).which are calculated separately.

5.2.2 Formulation of optimization problem based on the Parameters obtained

The control law in equation (4) was used to formulate the given weighting factor into an objective function in order to produce an optimized weigh for the controller input. The optimization problem's goal is to maximize gains while minimizing weight. k_p and k_i , for integral time absolute error minimization between the control input $u(t)$. On the basis of equation (4), the cost function was developed. The boundaries for the system variables were determined by considering the range derived from the implementation of PI without utilizing FOA. The following constraints are used to select the best solution:

$$4 < k_p < 4.5 \quad (5)$$

$$43 < k_i < 44 \quad (6)$$

Therefore, k_p and k_i are the weighting factor's parameters that need to be optimized in order to fulfill the goal.

5.2.3 Optimization of the weighting factor using FOA

The FOA algorithm was employed in this research to optimize the cost function parameters. Equation (4) serves as evaluation criteria for the optimality of the results obtained by FOA. Table 2 provides the FOA parameters used in this study.

Table 2: FOA Parameter

S/N	Parameters	Symbol	Value	Unit.
1.	Population	N	50
2.	Dimension	D	3
3.	Iteration	Itr	10
4.	Step Movement		Adaptive	
5.	Generation		50	

5.2.4 Simulation of the system model with the developed FOA-PI controller

Figure 4 shows the close loop system developed in Simulink/MATLAB that was used to simulate the developed PI with the two-stage battery under various initial circumstances (IC).

Figure 4: Simulink

6.0 RESULT

Presented in this section contains the results obtained when PI controller was applied within a specific range of charging and discharging of battery.

6.1 Proportional Integral Parameter Selection

PI controller was optimized to use FOA to find the best gains; ten iterations later, the optimal parameters were discovered as below.

Table 3: Optimal Parameters of PI

FOA Parameters	Value
Cost Function	1.4
K_p	-3.05
K_i	42.25

6.2 Simulation Results of FOA-PI and SISO-Fuzzy with the Two-stage Battery Model

The outcomes of the simulation for each of Smell Agent Optimization Proportional Integral (FOA-PI) control and Single Input Single Output Fuzzy Logic (SISO-Fuzzy Logic) control with two-stage battery system displayed in Figures 3 and 5 were acquired by taking into account the nominal current of 22A. The response of the battery current is shown in Figure 5

Figure 5: Battery Current

Figure 6 shows the graphs of state of charge of battery obtained from simulation

Figure 6: State of Charge (SOC) of the Battery

Figure 7 shows the graphs of load voltage obtained from simulation.

Figure 7: Load Voltage

Figure 8 shows the graphs of voltage source switch obtained from simulation.

Figure 8: Voltage Source Switch

6.3 Performance Comparison of the Developed FOA-PI based and SISO-Fuzzy

The performance of the controllers for the two-stage battery control system was assessed on the basis of root mean square error (RMSE) as reported in Muritala *et al.*, (2024). The performance of the developed Fruitfly Optimization Algorithm Proportional Integral (FOA-PI) controller and SISO-Fuzzy logic controller based on DC voltage regulation, battery voltage and battery reference control with respect to the performance metric were presented in Table 4

Table 4: Performance Comparison between the Developed FOA-PI and SISO-Fuzzy Logic Schemes

Performance Specification	Controller		Percentage Improvement (%)
	Developed FOA-PI	SISO-Fuzzy Logic	
DC Voltage Regulation	0.008	0.008	–
Battery Voltage	0.02	0.02	–
Battery Reference Control	0.691	0.769	6.91%

Table 4 summarizes the performance comparison of the developed FOA-PI and that of SISO-Fuzzy logic reported in the work of Muritala *et al.*, (2024). It can be observed from the Table 4 above that, the developed FOA-PI has the overall improvement of good battery reference control of 6.91% in RMSE when compared to the work reported by (Muritala *et al.*, 2024).

7.0 CONCLUSION

This research has presented the development an optimized proportional Integral controller for two-stage battery model. In Simulink, a two-stage battery model was developed PI and FOA were then used to adjust the gain parameters in an optimal battery control scheme. The MATLAB/Simulink software was utilized to the simulation in MATLAB2022b for the battery discharging rate to maintain the load voltage within the desired range of 48V. The performance evaluation of the results was carried out and compared to the two-stage battery system developed by (Muritala *et al.*,2022) in terms of root mean square error (RMSE).

The simulation results reveal that the developed FOA-PI has the overall improvement of good battery reference control of 6.91% in RMSE when compared to the work reported by (Muritala *et al.*, 2024

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